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A Critical Perspective on the Removal of the Teacher's Guidebooks from the Curriculum

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the Turkish Language teachers' views on the removal of teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum. This study employed case study, one of the qualitative research designs. The study group consisted of 66 Turkish Language teachers. The study group was formed using the maximum variation sampling, one of the purposeful sampling methods. A structured interview form developed by the researcher was used in collection of data. Content analysis was employed to analyze the data obtained from the participants. The majority of the participating teachers stated that they did not approve the removal of the teacher's guidebooks. Teachers expressed that they did not approve the removal of the teacher's guidebooks due to their positive contribution to the teaching of the lessons and preparation for the lesson, and due to their contribution to the course's standards, and stated that should be reprinted.

Keywords: Teacher's Guidebook, Turkish Language Teacher, Professional Teacher

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

The textbooks in Turkey have been constantly changing and are being updated with each new curriculum. The Ministry of National Education declared its transition from behaviorist approach to constructivist approach with a radical change made in the curricula in 2004 (MoNE [Ministry of National Education], 2004). With this change, there has been a transition from teacher-centered education to student-centered education. During the 2005-2006 academic year, textbooks were also changed along with the Turkish Language Curriculum, which was developed based on the constructivist approach and the theory of multiple intelligences. With this curriculum, a triple book model, in which the student textbook, student workbook and teacher's guidebook were prepared separately, was adopted (Durukan, 2009). Student textbooks included texts, student workbooks included activities, and teacher's guidebooks included additional activities, questions and directions to ensure effective use of student textbooks and student workbooks.

Used for a long time, the triple book model was abandoned after the works carried out in the last five years on the renewal of Turkish Language curriculum. The student textbook and the student workbook were combined into a single textbook, and the teacher's guidebook was removed altogether. This was partially implemented in the 2017-2018 academic year and implemented at all grade levels in the 2018-2019 academic year. Thus, the examination of the effect of the removal of teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum on teachers became the focal point of this study.

The teacher's guidebook is the main resource guiding the teacher in the planning, implementation and evaluation of learning activities. Developed in line with the objectives and explanations included in curricula, the teacher's guidebooks are works in print or electronic format including various instructions, explanations, exercises and activities that ensure the effective use of the student textbook (MoNE, 2015). These works help the teachers on how to present the subjects, establish the relationship between information, skills and ideas among students, and select activities to evaluate students' learning processes (Koseoglu et al., 2003).

Since the curricula, student textbooks and teacher's guidebooks in Turkey are determined by the MoNE, teachers do not have much of a leeway. Teachers do not take an active role in the preparation process of teacher's guidebooks. Therefore, they become the practitioners of the scenarios prepared by others for them. The instructions and practices given in the teacher's guidebooks significantly limit the role of teachers during the teaching process. Almost every step such as objectives, lesson plans, lesson scenarios, methods, techniques and assessment tools are presented to the teacher in a ready-made teacher's guidebook, and the teacher is expected to comply with them (Guner, 2011). This restriction of the role of the teacher turns teaching into a static job that does not require skills rather than a professional occupation. In other words, the teacher becomes a simple practitioner who fulfills the instructions rather than an expert who makes their own decisions during the teaching process (Ozoglu et al., 2013). Sari (2018) argued that this understanding will cause teachers to lose their professional control and turn them into unqualified people. According to the results of an important study conducted in our country on this subject, more than half of the teachers (54%) believe that they are passive practitioners of the decisions made from the center (Yurdakul et al., 2016).

Contrary to the arguments in the literature that teacher's guidebooks prevent teachers' autonomy, there are studies in which teachers stated that teacher's guidebooks are useful. Teachers expressed that they receive support from teacher's guidebooks on many subjects, especially on planning, method and technique, and that they want to continue to receive support (Genc et al., 2014; Gur, 2014; Gocer, 2011; Guner, 2011). The fact that the teacher's guidebooks have just been removed from the curriculum makes teachers' experiences and opinions about the teacher's guidebooks important. There are only a few studies on this issue. It can be said that the effect of not using teacher's guidebooks on teachers should be addressed and evaluated with more studies. It is believed that the present study will contribute to the discussion that teacher's guidebooks limit teachers' autonomy and will raise awareness of teachers' feelings, thoughts and expectations about the reuse of teacher's guidebooks.

The autonomy of teachers during the teaching process contributes positively to their professional performance, school climate and students. Teachers who are given authority can structure a more purposeful and student-centered education process in line with student needs and desires (Colak & Altinkurt, 2017; Frostenson, 2015; TED-Mem 2015). The studies on PISA revealed a positive relationship between country achievement scores, and teacher and school autonomy. Particular attention is drawn to the role of teacher autonomy in Finland's high achievement in PISA (Sahlberg, 2011). Many studies put forth a positive relationship between teachers' perceived autonomy levels and self-efficacy levels (Kosar, 2015), their job satisfaction (Altinyurt et al., 2017), the positive working climate (Ingersoll, 1996), and their competence and professionalism (Pearson & Moomaw, 2005). When teachers use their autonomy to realize what is required for students' education, students can also develop responsibility for their own learning. Although teacher autonomy has many positive contributions, there are also many factors affecting the autonomy level. The centralized structure of the education system, restrictive legislation and regulations, curricula and textbooks developed by the central authority can limit teacher autonomy (Bumen, 2019).

1.2 Study Objectives

The purpose of this study is to determine the Turkish Language teachers' views on the removal of teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum. The views of the Turkish Language teachers, who have used the teacher's guidebooks before, are significant. In the study, teachers thoughts about the removal of teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum will be questioned. For this purpose, answers to the following questions will be sought:

- 1) How do teachers assess that the removal of the teacher's guidebooks?
- 2) Why do teachers assess this way?

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

This study employed case study, one of the qualitative research designs. Yin (2014) described case study as a research method that is used to answer how and why questions. In this study, the case study design was chosen as it was investigated what Turkish language teachers think about removing the teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum and why they think so. Thus, the advantages and limitations of these books, and whether or not they should be used were investigated from the perspective of those who knew them best.

2.2 Participants

The participants of the study were determined using the maximum variation sampling, one of the purposeful sampling methods. The criteria used to determine the study participants were to use the teacher's guidebooks for at least one year and to voluntarily participate in the study. The maximum sampling method was chosen to ensure that the study group consisted of people with different seniority and different working conditions. Since teachers' experiences and opinions about teacher's guidebooks can be affected by the seniority and sex variables, it was aimed to diversify the study group in terms of these variables. It is believed that this diversity will contribute to a better understanding of the experiences and opinions about the phenomenon examined in the study.

In the study, individuals who filled out the electronic data collection form shared on e-mail were reached in order to ensure maximum diversity. There are several reasons why the study group was formed in this way. First, since the use of teacher's guidebooks, which were developed by different publishing houses, varied from city to city, it was aimed to diversify the study group as much as possible in terms of city. E-mail was believed to be the easiest way to reach participants living in different cities. Second, since it was believed that the teachers would not sincerely express some of their views, thinking that their identities would be disclosed during the face-to-face meeting, the participants were reached via social media. Participants varied in terms of the sex, seniority and city of employment variables. 39 males and 27 females from 8 cities from different regions of Turkey participated in the study. Gender and seniority information about the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Personal Information of Participants

Gender	2-4 years	5-8 years	9-12 years	13-16 years	17-20 years	21 years and over
Female	9	6	4	4	2	2
Male	3	14	12	5	3	2
Total	12	20	16	9	5	4

2.3 Data Collection Tools

In the study, developed by the researcher, Teacher Views on Teacher's Guidebooks Questionnaire (TVTGG) including open-ended questions was administered as a data collection tool. Before the questions in the questionnaire were developed, similar studies in the literature (Gocer, 2011; Gocer & Akturk, 2015; Sari, 2018)

were examined and utilized. Considering the purpose of the study and related studies, a draft form consisting of open-ended questions questioning teachers' opinions about teacher's guidebooks was developed. The form included opinion questions aiming to understand the person's interpretation process (Patton, 2014).

In order to ensure the content validity of the form developed by the researcher, expert opinion was asked. Three experts with a Ph.D. in the field of Turkish education examined the draft form in terms of the draft being understandable and the level of coverage of the researched subject. The interview form was finalized in line with the recommendations of the experts and became ready for administration. The interview form included two questions about their opinions on the removal and reprinting of the teacher's guidebooks. In addition, personal questions about participants' sex, professional experience, city of employment and online meeting request were also included in the interview form.

2.4. Process

Study data were collected between September 16, 2020 and September 26, 2020. The questionnaire developed online in the Google Drive application was sent teachers' e-mail. Participants were asked whether they would voluntarily fill out the electronic form shared with them after writing a directive explaining the purpose of the study and the confidentiality protocol. Teachers who wanted to participate answered the questionnaire by clicking the link. After that, a 40-minute meeting was held by video conference method with 15 participants who accepted the online meeting request in the interview form. Video conference recordings and electronic forms filled out by participants were stored in a folder.

2.5 Data Analysis

The study data were analyzed by content analysis. First, preliminary analysis of the forms from 73 participants, which were obtained via the electronic environment, were performed. During this analysis, some of the participants' forms (seven participants) were not included in the study due to the lack of justified explanations and plain and superficial answers provided by them. During the in-depth examination, the participant forms and the recordings were read more than once and common codes were determined. Themes were determined by developing upper categories from the obtained codes. Finally, the qualitative data obtained were quantified and tabulated by taking the frequency values of the data. Since each participant can give more than one answer, the calculated frequency value of the codes shows the frequency value of the answers.

2.6 Validity and Reliability

Certain measures were taken to ensure the validity, reliability and compliance of the study with ethical principles. In order to ensure the internal validity of the study, analyst variation and expert review were performed. Analyst variation refers to the use of multiple analysts to control the findings (Patton, 2014). In this regard, 10 randomly determined forms were coded separately by the researcher and a teacher with a master's degree in Turkish Language Education, and then the codes developed by each researcher were checked by the other researcher. The codes that were determined to be different are discussed rearranged accordingly. Another validity and reliability strategy used in the study was expert review. This technique is a peer interview about the overlap of the raw findings and comments obtained (Merriam, 2013). The researcher presented the interview forms he deciphered and the codes and themes he obtained for the approval of an expert in the field of qualitative research. At the confirmation meeting, feedback was received regarding the codes and themes determined by the researcher.

For the transmissibility of the study results to similar groups or environments (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013), the statements of the participants were presented with direct quotations, and various characteristics of the participants were given. In selecting direct quotations, the criterion was that the quotation included proof supporting the relevant theme and code in the best way and the quotation was a sufficient example. Each participating teacher was given a code name (such as P1: Participant 1). Thus the participants' personal information was kept confidential. In order to increase the validity and reliability of the study, the findings

obtained from the analysis were presented without comment. Discussion of the study results was based on basic findings.

Attention was paid to voluntary participation and confidentiality of the participants' identities in order to conduct the study in accordance with ethical principles. The study purpose and how the questions would be answered were explained in detail in the directive of the questionnaire. The questionnaire also stated that the data obtained from the study would not be shared with second persons.

3. Results

"How do teachers assess that the removal of the teacher's guidebooks?" the answers given by the participants to this question consist of codes gathered under four themes. The themes and codes within the scope of these themes are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Teachers' Views on the Removal of the Teacher's Guidebooks

Theme	Code	f
Contribution to teaching of the lesson (f=45)	Instructions explaining what to do during the teaching process	17
	Explanations on how to do the activities and exercises	13
	Original methods, techniques and activities	12
	Listening texts	3
Contribution to preparation for the lesson (f=35)	To have ready lesson plans	26
	To have the necessary preliminary information about the lesson	9
Insufficiency/nonconformity of teacher's guidebook (f=30)	To have directing excessive	11
	Explaining certain activities and instructions in great detail	8
	Some activities and instructions not appropriate	7
	Incomplete and erroneous explanations	4
Contribution to lesson's standard (f=13)	Ensured a standard lesson	7
	Led to a monotonous lesson	6

According to Table 2, teachers' views on the removal of the teacher's guidebooks were mostly gathered under the themes of contribution to teaching of the lesson (f=45), contribution to preparation for the lesson (f=35), insufficiency/nonconformity of teacher's guidebook (f=30) and contribution to lesson's standard (f=13), respectively.

3.1 Theme 1: Contribution to Teaching of the Lesson

Under the contribution to teaching of the lesson theme, teachers stated that they did not find the removal of the teacher's guidebooks appropriate since they made it easy to teach the lesson. Many teachers (f=17) considered the instructions provided in the teacher's guidebooks that directed them on what to do during the teaching process advantageous. They particularly emphasized the importance of the instructions for the newcomers to the profession. One of the teachers (P41) explained the function of the instructions using the following words, "The teacher's guidebooks helped us during the teaching process. The instructions were drawing our roadmap. The teacher was teaching more efficiently by adding his own knowledge and experience. It was a guide, especially for newcomers to the profession." Another teacher (P8) expressed compared the instructions in the teacher's guidebooks to a compass and stated, "Having a compass in the hand of the teacher while he or she was trying to help the student acquire an objective made it easier to reach the goal."

The teachers pointed out the function of the instructions and explanations in the teacher's guidebooks and stated that they should be reprinted. Teachers mentioned that they did not follow all the instructions in the teacher's guidebooks, that they preferred to use only some of them, and that these instructions were very useful especially for those who were new to the profession. On this, one teacher (P55) said, "The teacher's guidebook is not a copying method, only a guide, and every person sometimes needs a guide. Even if it wouldn't be right to stick

with it completely, it guide sets a road map for you.” In parallel with this, another teacher (P27) told, “The teacher’s guidebook would be appropriate for teachers who are not experienced in teaching in terms of guiding them. Directive and warning information will be useful.”

A significant number of teachers (f=13) mentioned that some activities and exercises in the student textbooks were complex, incomprehensible and contradictory, and teacher’s guidebooks should be used to understand them. P40 said, “I needed to use guidebook last year. I don't even understand what some activities want. How can the child understand? There is definitely a need for a teacher’s guidebook for such activities.” Similarly P55 explained this situation with the following:

Sometimes I cannot even establish a connection between the texts and the questions in the student textbooks. I wonder about their meaning. So, I cannot understand how I am expected to give correct information to the students when I cannot understand the student textbook. Certainly, books like this should be given with a teacher’s guidebook.

Some teachers (f=12) expressed that there were different and original activities, methods and strategies in the teacher’s guidebooks, which facilitated the teaching process, and therefore they did not find it appropriate to remove the teacher’s guidebooks. Teachers want to start using the teacher’s guidebooks again as they provide a variety of activities and methods. P10 said, “Educational science is a science that is constantly evolving and changing. I needed a guide book, especially on topics and activities that new approaches in education should have been known.” One teacher (P15) explained the originality of the activities and methods in the teacher’s guidebooks as follows:

An objective can be acquired by students with different methods and activities. However, the teacher’s original activity may not always be better than the activity ideas in teacher’s guidebooks. In this respect, I believe teacher’s guidebooks are a helpful resource that can be used in classroom activities.

Another teacher (P32) mentioned that the activities and methods in the teacher’s guidebooks are the source of creative thinking and said, “Thinking different activities and thinking creatively are not everyone’s cup of tea. We were at least starting from what was ready and gave it a shape.” Although the teacher’s guidebooks restricted the freedom during teaching, P27 stated the importance of teacher’s guidebooks in terms of method:

Although teacher’s guidebooks prevented teachers from teaching the lesson freely by providing every point during the teaching process in detail, at least they were guiding. The teachers benefited greatly from the teacher’s guidebooks due to their lack of knowledge about methods and techniques.

Some teachers (f=3) considered it an advantage to have transcriptions of the audio materials related to the lesson in the teacher’s guidebooks and therefore it is not appropriate to remove teacher’s guidebook. Explaining his views on the listening texts, one of the teachers (P60) stated,

The listening texts were given in the teacher’s guidebooks. This is important for equality of opportunity. There is no smart board, internet, or a sound system in every school. We would have the written version of the listening texts. When technical facilities were insufficient, we could teach by reading aloud.

3.2 Theme 2: Contribution to Preparation for the Lesson

Under the lesson preparation for the lesson theme, teachers (f=26) emphasized that it was an advantage for them to have ready lesson plans in the teacher’s guidebooks. Many teachers mentioned that they did not have to prepare lesson plans when there were teacher’s guidebooks, and that this provided them with an important convenience. The teachers emphasized that they were required to prepare daily lesson plans by the school administration since the teacher’s guidebooks were removed from the curriculum. Thus, they did not approve the removal. The teachers explained this issue:

I do not find it right to remove the teacher’s guidebooks. An application that was good and that provided was abandoned for no reason. I see the only reason as the cost of the teacher’s guidebooks. We are returning back to the old days. Preparing daily plans is constantly wasting paper every week. It is very unnecessary to reproduce the daily plan separately for yourself and for the administration. (P33)

I want teacher’s guidebooks used again books because they reduce the paperwork for us and makes it easier for us to focus on the lesson. In addition, since I didn’t have to go to the trouble of preparing

lesson plans, I was able to research different activities and methods that would help students understand the subjects. (P10)

In addition, some teachers (f=9) emphasized that teachers' guide books have the necessary preliminary information about the lesson and this situation contributed to their preparation for the lesson. One of the teachers (P63) stated that even going unprepared to the lesson was not a problem when there was a teacher's guidebook and said:

The greatest contribution of the teacher's guidebooks was to help me with how to prepare before the lesson. On the other hand, even if the teacher was unprepared for the lesson, he did not suffer from it during teaching as long as there was the teacher's guidebook.

3.3 Theme 3: Insufficiency/nonconformity of Teacher's Guidebook

Under the insufficiency/nonconformity of teacher's guidebook theme, the negative aspects of teacher's guidebooks are emphasized. Some teachers criticized the excessive detail of teacher's guidebooks and the quality of their activities and instructions, based on their experiences in the past years. Teachers want the problems they have identified with regard to the guidebooks to be eliminated and to be updated.

Mentioning that the teacher's guidebooks were excessively detailed, the teachers stated that they were uncomfortable with the teacher's guidebooks directing them excessively (f=11) and explaining certain activities and instructions in great detail (f=8). The teachers considered the instructions explaining how to do even the simplest task and giving the answer to each question in the guide as excessive. On this subject, one teacher (P1) said, "Providing the answers to even the simplest questions and explaining the activities in great detail made the teacher's guidebooks boring." Similarly, P58 stated, "It is unnecessary to explain everything in detail. It caused us to miss important points because there was too much text. The teacher's guidebooks should have been."

Some instructions and activities not appropriate for class and region (f=7), and incomplete and erroneous explanations (n=4) are the other disliked aspects of the teacher's guidebooks. The teachers also stated that the content of the teacher's guidebooks was not appropriate, and if the content would be updated, the teacher's guidebooks should be reprinted. Regarding this issue, P47 said:

We did not apply every instruction literally, of course. It changed according to class and school conditions. The teacher's guidebooks were developed considering all schools were at the same level. We had lower its standards for our school. There were activities and suggestions we didn't do. So the content would be updated and the teacher's guidebooks should be reprinted.

3.4 Theme 4: Contribution to Lesson's Standard

Under the contribution to lesson's standard theme, there were opposing teachers' views. According to some teachers, teacher's guidebooks ensured a standard Turkish Language lesson (f=7), whereas for some teachers, teacher's guidebooks led to a monotonous and uniform Turkish Language lesson (f=6).

Among the teacher views on not wanting the teacher's guidebooks to be reprinted, the belief that using teacher's guidebooks was expecting everything to be handed on a silver platter and that they prevent teachers' freedom came to the fore. One teacher (P22) said, "For me, there is no need for teacher's guidebooks. Teachers should go to their classrooms preparing for their own lessons. The teacher's guidebook inevitably makes us teachers a little lazy." Similarly, one teacher (P5) told, "No, I don't want them to be reprinted. Instead, a platform like EBA should be created on the internet for teachers only." In addition, P6 stated, "No, I don't want them to be reprinted. We now have the opportunity to freely teach our classes. The teacher's guidebooks prevent us from teaching the lesson ourselves." P22 said:

I find it correct to remove the teacher's guidebooks. The teacher should teach the lesson according to his classroom environment. The teacher's guidebooks were forcing a certain region into a single type of Turkish Language lesson. Teachers tended to go to class without preparation.

A significant number of teachers ($f=7$) expressed that the explanations and information in the teacher's guidebook made them feel like they were teaching a standard Turkish Language class. In fact, P53 said, "I would definitely want the teacher's guidebooks. They are important because they supervise and show the shortcomings of the teacher in terms of activities, planning and program," whereas P42 said, "Yes, I would like to have them back because they would reduce my workload and provide unity between teachers. There won't be discussions on who taught what to students." In addition, P47 stated,

Maybe we wouldn't need a teacher's guidebook if every school had the same conditions, but unfortunately our schools don't have the same conditions. So, in a school where there is no smart board and no technological devices, I think we need a teacher's guidebook, having only the annual plan is not enough.

4. Discussion

Evaluated within the framework of the relevant literature, the results of this study, which aimed to determine the Turkish Language teachers' views on the removal of teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum are presented below.

Most of the teachers participating in the study stated that they made use of the teacher's guidebooks especially in terms of teaching of the lesson, preparation for the lesson and the lesson's standard, and therefore they did not find it appropriate to remove the teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum. Many teachers expressed that they did not find it right to remove the teacher's guidebooks, especially because it takes time to make a lesson plan and prepare for the lesson, and that they should be reprinted. It is believed that school administrations wanting the teachers prepare daily lesson plans is after this decision. Similar to this finding, previous studies revealed that teachers find daily lesson planning unnecessary detailed and time-consuming work and a formality (İsman & Eskicumali, 2003; Ozturk, 2012).

All of the participating teachers participating in the study asserted that the teacher's guidebooks contributed to them in various ways in the past years. The instructions in the teacher's guidebooks explaining what teachers do during the teaching process were found beneficial by many teachers in this study. Various study results in this field also put forth that teachers benefit from teacher's guidebooks and have positive thoughts about them (Gocer, 2011; Gocer & Akturk, 2015; Guner, 2011; Gur, 2014; Sari, 2018). The instructions in the teacher's guidebooks that explain to the smallest detail what the teacher should do during the teaching process actually restrict teacher's autonomy during the teaching process. The studies conducted in Turkey on teacher autonomy argued that teachers felt autonomous during the teaching process (Colak et al., 2017) and they did not believe the teacher's guidebooks interfere with their autonomy (Gur, 2014, Sari, 2018).

In his study based on teachers' views, Gur (2014) revealed that most of the teachers did not believe the teacher's guidebooks limited their professional autonomy. The information and explanations in the teacher's guidebooks were followed by the teachers. However, they were not being followed completely. The participating teachers in this study also read the explanations and suggestions in the teacher's guidebooks, applied some of them according to the needs of their own classes, and did not apply the rest. A study conducted with Turkish Language teachers determined that all of the participating teachers referred to the teacher's guidebooks, but some of the teachers used the teacher's guidebooks more and some used less (Gocer, 2011). It can be said that using the teacher's guidebooks extensively and performing the teacher role given in these books without questioning is against teacher autonomy, but looking at the information and explanations in these books for advice is not against teacher autonomy.

Teachers have positive attitudes towards teacher's guidebooks as well as some negative attitudes. The majority of teachers participating in this study expressed that the teacher's guidebooks were overly detailed, contained excessive direction, and that the activities and instructions were generally similar, and some of them were not applicable. These findings are in parallel with the results of previous studies (Akkocaoglu, 2009; Ilik, 2011; Sert, 2012). The literature argued that activities and instructions are included in the teacher's guidebooks in similar forms in every theme and text (Uysal, 2012), that teacher's guidebooks did not give enough chance to the teacher

to choose, stretch or change the activities, and that some of the activities are not appropriate for the opportunities the students have living in small residential areas (Akkocaoglu, 2009; Sert, 2012). All these negative criticisms actually show that the teacher's guidebooks limit teacher autonomy in some aspects.

Although the teachers participating in the current study directed various criticisms towards the teacher's guidebooks, majority of them stated that they needed a teacher's guidebooks within the last year. Teachers mentioned that they needed teacher's guidebooks especially in terms of lesson plans, instructions, activities and method variety. Since the teachers in Turkey use the ready-made teaching methods and techniques found in the curricula and teacher's guidebooks, they are at-risk of not having the need to improve themselves in terms of new methods, techniques and methods (Mavis Sevim et al., 2017). In this context, it can be argued that teacher's guidebooks are in the way for teachers to research different methods, activities and practices, and to develop various innovations in line with the needs of their classes.

Almost all of the teachers who participated in the study stated that the teacher's guidebooks should be reprinted in the near future. The findings of the studies conducted after the removal of the teacher's guidebooks from the curriculum (Sugumlu et al., 2019; Yurtbakan & Ozsevgec, 2019) support the findings of the current study. According to the result of a recent study on the necessity of teacher's guidebooks, the majority of classroom teachers (81.05%) said that they were necessary (Yurtbakan & Ozsevgec, 2019). As a result of a study conducted with Turkish Language teachers, reusing middle school teacher's Turkish Language guidebooks came to the fore (Sugumlu et al., 2019). When all these findings are evaluated together, it can be said that although the teachers criticize the teacher's guidebooks, they adopted them significantly and want to use them again. This can be interpreted as the teachers want to continue using the teacher's guidebooks since they have various deficiencies and inadequacies in selecting methods and techniques, designing different activities, planning and implementing lessons.

It can be thought that teacher's guidebooks were removed by the MoNE in order to increase teacher autonomy and encourage teachers to be more creative in their lessons. With the removal of the teacher's guidebooks, teachers were expected to make daily lesson plans according to the needs of their classes, to search for methods and materials appropriate to the level of their students and use them. However, based on the views expressed by the teachers in this study, it can be said that very few teachers acted in accordance with this goal. Teachers should be individuals who can learn, solve problems and conduct research on their own in order to obtain the expected benefit from removing the teacher's guidebooks and increasing teacher autonomy (Yavuz, 2016). The following recommendations can be made considering teachers' habits of following the teacher's guidebooks, and the need for them to do research on subjects related to teaching process and for them to be professionals who can act autonomously. First, the practice of teacher's guidebooks should continue with some changes. Teacher's guidebooks should be developed flexibly, and should be designed as a reference work that can give new ideas to teachers, away from the supervision of inspectors and administrative management. The teacher's guidebooks should not be thought of as a strict program that should be followed by the teachers. On the contrary, they should be designed as a help book giving teachers new ideas and offering various suggestions. Second, instead of providing repeated activities with each text and unit or offering explanations about how to do even the simplest activities, teacher's guidebooks should include examples that will offer creative ideas to teachers, explanations on how to implement the lesson objectives within the framework of the conditions specific to schools, regions and classes, and suggestions to increase teacher autonomy. Third, it can be said that teachers should increase their professional knowledge, improve their research and learning skills, and follow scientific developments in their fields in order to better display autonomous behaviors during the teaching process (Colak et al., 2017). Finally, in future studies, teacher practices after the removal of the teacher's guidebooks can be examined with longitudinal studies, and the positive and negative aspects of this removal can be examined in more depth.

4.1. Limitation of the Study

One of the limitations of this study is that teachers' views on teacher's guidebooks were determined solely based on the views of Turkish Language teachers. Since the contents of the teacher's guidebooks for different courses may differ significantly from each other, the study focused only on one course's teacher's edition in order to

obtain more in-depth information. For this reason, in order to obtain more generalizable results in future studies, the views of teachers from different branches on teacher's guidebooks can be examined in quantitative or mixed design studies with the help of questionnaires and scales.

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